

DEVELOPMENT OF A TECHNOLOGY FOR A COMPLEX COMPOSITION SUNSCREEN CREAM BASED ON LOCAL RAW MATERIALS

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Abstract: The medicinal substances and bases included in sunscreen creams differ in their physicochemical properties. According to the State Pharmacopoeia, before incorporating medicinal substances into the composition of photoprotective creams, their physicochemical characteristics must be studied.

Keywords: cream, tea leaves, technology, sesame oil

Introduction: The solid components in suspension-type creams are insoluble in water and in the base. Therefore, these substances must be thoroughly ground in a mortar and mixed with the base. If the active solid components make up up to 4% of the preparation, they are crushed with the help of an auxiliary liquid. According to Deryagin's rule, the volume of auxiliary liquid should equal half the volume of the substances being processed. The auxiliary liquid should be as close as possible in nature to the base. If the base is hydrocarbon-based — Vaseline oil is used as an auxiliary liquid. If oil-based — peach oil, sunflower oil, or sesame oil is used. If the base is water-soluble — water or glycerin is used. If the solid medicinal ingredient is more than 4%, it is first ground with half the required amount of melted base, then the remaining base is added.

This type of mixed cream belongs to multiphase topical medications, where active substances can be in dissolved, suspended, or emulsified forms simultaneously. The preparation technology must take into account the physicochemical properties of the ingredients. In preparing the "Fito" photoprotective cream, green tea infusion was used as a base [1].

Materials and Methods of the Study:

To obtain a decoction in a 1:10 ratio from tea leaves, the AU-3 infusor (Russia) was used. The VK-300.1 electronic balance was used to determine the average weight of the products. A mortar was used in the cream preparation process.

Results: To prepare the green tea decoction, the water absorption coefficient of the tea leaves was determined. For this, 10.0 g of green tea leaves (crushed to 3–5 mm) were placed in the infusor with 100 ml of purified room temperature water, boiled for 15 minutes, and filtered while hot.

This is because tannins in tea leaves dissolve better in hot water. After filtration, the liquid is squeezed out from the infusor and its volume is measured. Based on the loss, it was determined that to prepare a 5% green tea decoction, 5.0 g of dried tea leaves and 107 ml of purified water are required [2].

Formula Passport (1st Composition):

Green tea infusion – 10.0 ml

Phenyl salicylate – 2.0 g

Zinc oxide – 5.0 g

Vaseline – 16.5 g

Preparation Process:

10.0 ml Green tea infusion is added to a mortar and mixed with anhydrous lanolin. Separately, vaseline is melted in a porcelain bowl, then 5.0 g of zinc oxide is dispersed into 5.0 g of vaseline in another heated mortar. In a separate mortar, 2.0 g of phenyl salicylate is mixed with the remaining melted vaseline until fully dissolved. The resulting mixture is added to the mortar

containing zinc oxide. Then the lanolin-tea mixture is added, followed by the gradual addition of the remaining vaseline. This results in a mixed-type cream: Tea and lanolin form an emulsion, Zinc oxide and vaseline form a suspension, Salol and vaseline form a solution. After combining all parts, a homogeneous mixed cream is formed.

The quality of the finished cream is evaluated. It is packaged in brown plastic containers with screw caps and labeled: "For external use" and "Store in a cool, dark place."

II-Composition:

Green tea infusion – 10.0 ml

Phenyl salicylate – 2.0 g

Zinc oxide – 5.0 g

Sodium tetraborate – 1.0 g

Beeswax – 3.0 g

Sesame oil – 29.0 g

Total weight: 50.0 g

Preparation Process:

3.0 g of beeswax is melted in a porcelain dish at 63–65°C in a water bath. Half of the sesame oil is added to the melted wax and filtered while hot. In another preheated mortar, 2.0 g of phenyl salicylate is added, and then mixed with the melted wax and sesame oil until the salicylate dissolves completely. In a second heated mortar, 5.0 g of zinc oxide is dispersed with half its amount of sesame oil (per Deryagin's rule).

The wax–oil–salicylate mixture is added and stirred thoroughly. Separately, 10 ml of green tea infusion (preheated to 45–50°C) is prepared. Sodium tetraborate is dissolved at 80–85°C, then gradually added to the mixture and stirred until a white foamy cream is formed. The cream is left to cool in the mortar for 1–2 hours.

Any droplets forming on the sides of the mortar are remixed for proper emulsification. The cream is evaluated for quality, packaged in brown plastic containers with screw-on caps, and labeled: "For external use." "Store in a dark, cool place."

Conclusion:

The compatibility of medicinal and auxiliary ingredients in photoprotective creams was studied, and an optimal formulation was developed.

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